

1 **Transcription in the hepatocyte-like stem cell.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the hepatocyte-like stem cell during the course of
7 differentiation from induced pluripotent stem cells. These hepatocyte-like stem cells expressed *Havcr1*,
8 *Cd109* and *Cd24*, *Cdh17* and *Itga2*. The cells were metabolically different with expression of *Fmo1* and
9 *Fmo2*, induction of *Arg1* and *Kynu* but silencing of *Ass1*, *Tat*, and *Hal*. The cells expressed *Sox4*, were
10 *Ldha*⁺ and produced the tissue-restricted antigen *Alb*.

11 Citations

12 1. Feigelstock, D., Thompson, P., Mattoo, P., Zhang, Y. and Kaplan, G.G., 1998. The human
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